

Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 36):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁵

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 10 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 + - * / ^ ()

Digits 1 up to 9 occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89$ $9^{(8-7)}*6/(-5+4+3)+21$

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45^{-(6^7)}+8-9)$	$(98+7^{-(6^5)}+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9)$	$(98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^{-(6^7)}+8-9)$	$(98+7^{-(6^5)}+4)*(3-2-1)$
$-(1+2+3)*(45^{(6^7)}+8-9)$	$(98+7^{(6^5)}+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-(7+8-9)))$	$-((9-(8+7-6))*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Note

Authors consider genuine crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial.

Authors do not guaranty:

- Published crazy sequential representations are the shortest in existence.
- Published crazy sequential representations are in their simplest form.
- Unavailable crazy sequential representations do not exists.

Previously

Previously ^{6,7} authors attempted to identify 3 types of crazy sequential representations (without division/potentialiation/concatenation) for the integers from -11111 up to 11111.

Increasing Crazy Sequential Representations					
	CSR by Inder Taneja	Shortest Overall	Shortest Without Division	Shortest Without Potentiation	Shortest Without Concatenation
1531	$1+(234+5)*6+7+89$	$12^3/4*5-6-7*89$	$12-3+4^5-6+7*8*9$	$-12*3+4*56*7+8-9$	$1+2^3+4^5-6+7*8*9$
3650	$12+34*(5+6+7+89)$	$1-234-5+6^7/8/9$	$-12-3^4+5+6*7*89$	$-1-23*4+5+6*7*89$	$(-1+2-3*4)*(5-6*7*8)+9$
5263	$(1+2)^3+4^5+6*78*9$	$1^2-3+45/6*78*9$	$12+(3*4+5+6*7)*89$	$-1+2-3+45/6*78*9$	$1+2+3-(-4^5*(6-7/8))-9$
7891	$(1+(2*3)^4+5)*6+7+8*9$	$1^2+3*4*5/6*789$	$1+(-2-3+4+5+6)*789$	$-1+2+3*4*5/6*789$	$1*2-(-3-4^5+6*7)*8+9$

Decreasing Crazy Sequential Representations					
	CSR by Inder Taneja	Shortest Overall	Shortest Without Division	Shortest Without Potentiation	Shortest Without Concatenation
1531	$98*(7+6)+5+4*3*21$	$9+8*765/4-3^2+1$	$9-8+76*5*4+3^2+1$	$9+8+76*5*4-3*2/1$	$9*8+7-6+(5+4)^3*2^1$
3650	$98*(7+6*5)+4*3*2*1$	$98/7*65*4+3^2+1$	$9+8*7*65-4+3+2^1$	$9+8*7*65-4+3+2/1$	$9*8*7*6+5^4+3-2/1$
5263	$(9*8+7)*65+4^3*2*1$	$987/6^(5-4)*32-1$	$987*6^(-5+4)*32-1$	$(9*8+7)*65+4*32*1$	$9*8+7+6^5*4/3/2*1$
7891	$9*8+7+6^5+4+32*1$	$9*876+54/3^2+1$	$9*876-5+4+3^2-1$	$9*876+5-4+3*2/1$	$9*8+7+6^5+4*3^2*1$

Increasing Crazy Sequential Representations					
	Shortest Overall	Shortest Without Division	Shortest Without Potentiation	Shortest Without Concatenation	
-3897	$12*3-45-6^7/8/9$	$1-2^3*4*5-6*7*89$	$(-123-4)*5*6-78-9$	$1+2-3-4-5-6^7/8/9$	
-8182	$1^23+4^5/(6-7)*8+9$	$1-2^3*4^5+(6-7)^8*9$	$-1+(-23-4)*(56*7-89)$	$1-2^(3+4*5-6-7)*8+9$	
-8650	$1-2^3/4^5-5-6*78+9$	$(-12^3+4)*5+6*7-8*9$	$-1*-2*(34-(56*78-9))$	$-1+(-2+3-4^5+6+7*8)*9$	
-9423	$-123*45-6^7/8/9$	$(-1+23+4^5)*(6-7-8)-9$	$(-12-3)*(-4/5+6+7*89)$	$(-1+2-(3+4^5+6+7*8))*9$	
-3897	$12*3-45-6^7/8/9$	$1-2^3*4*5-6*7*89$	$(-123-4)*5*6-78-9$	$1+2-3-4-5-6^7/8/9$	

Decreasing Crazy Sequential Representations					
	Shortest Overall	Shortest Without Division	Shortest Without Potentiation	Shortest Without Concatenation	
-3897	$9*(87-65/4*32)^1$	$-987+6-54^(3-2+1)$	$9*87-65*-4*(3-21)$	$-9+8-7-6^5/(4-3)/2-1$	
-7293	$9*8*7-6^5/(4-3)-21$	$9*8*7-6^5(4-3)-21$	$-9*-8*(7+6*-54/3)-21$	$-9*-8*7-6^5+(-4-3)*(2+1)$	
-8182	$9-8*7*65/4*3^2-1$	$9-(8+7-6-5)^4*32+1$	$-98*(76+5+4-3/2)+1$	$9+8*(7-6-5-4)^3*2+1$	
-8650	$98/7-6*(5-43)^2/1$	$(-987+6+5*4)*3^2-1$	$9+8+(-7-6*-5+4)*-321$	$-9*(8-7+6*-5*-4^3/2)-1$	
-3897	$9*(87-65/4*32)^1$	$-987+6-54^(3-2+1)$	$9*87-65*-4*(3-21)$	$-9+8-7-6^5/(4-3)/2-1$	

Previously missing increasing crazy sequential representations (for $\emptyset$ up to 11111):

	Only pseudo crazy sequential representation	No crazy sequential representation
Without Division		10958,11027
Without Potentiation	5818,6538,6988,7526,7924,7987,8170,8269,8324,8468,8561,8564,8797,8824,8860,8966,8986,9202,9220,9236,9254,9258,9304,9382,9716,9772,9781,9886,9904,9914,9916,9920,9931,10016,10018,10082,10267,10298,10310,10388,10490,10550,10645,10676,10748,10844,10918,10984,11030,11072	8312,9238,9986,10838,10840,10886,10958,11002,11027
Without Concatenation	3308,3820,4262,4444,4732,4749,4835,4894,5222,5288,5314,5317,5333,5350,5429,5486,5528,5613,5674,5708,5709,5771,5790,5811,5843,5884,6022,6330,6388,6662,6747,6773,6789,6798,6812,6818,6844,6853,6854,6863,6934,6974,6976,6988,6997,7286,7314,7321,7329,7334,7340,7358,7364,7388,7430,7437,7456,7458,7465,7467,7484,7486,7526,7537,7571,7591,7612,7621,7628,7654,7664,7676,7699,7716,7724,7732,7907,7923,7924,7949,7950,7961,7962,7963,7969,7977,8013,8018,8020,8027,8030,8035,8038,8040,8042,8044,8062,8069,8269,8341,8366,8393,8422,8437,8492,8508,8558,8588,8589,8590,8598,8618,8637,8644,8654,8656,8698,8716,8723,8725,8726,8734,8762,8781,8799,8800,8813,8836,8841,8860,8866,8878,8887,8890,8899,8914,8922,8942,8948,8957,8958,8959,8967,8987,8989,9041,9042,9049,9092,9122,9184,9238,9319,9425,9426,9427,9507,9509,9518,9526,9553,9563,9568,9570,9571,9584,9592,9597,9618,9619,9628,9631,9634,9680,9705,9707,9714,9715,9716,9722,9723,9724,9725,9741,9742,9787,9795,9797,9798,9802,9803,9817,9823,9824,9881,9883,9890,9892,9896,9903,9916,9919,9924,9931,9932,9934,9939,9941,9944,9946,9950,9957,9958,9968,9969,9970,9987,10022,10023,10036,10046,10047,10048,10049,10052,10074,10077,10086,10094,10117,10154,10202,10253,10257,10266,10283,10284,10286,10288,10309,10346,10347,10355,10356,10372,10379,10380,10401,10447,10452,10462,10466,10470,10477,10480,10482,10483,10484,10490,10492,10502,10508,10509,10514,10517,10525,10526,10534,10535,10538,10542,10545,10550,10558,10559,10560,10562,10570,10573,10576,10579,10599,10614,10616,10622,10628,10631,10632,10635,10670,10671,10675,10677,10712,10713,10717,10739,10740,10741,10747,10756,10766,10770,10775,10780,10787,10792,10798,10804,10807,10820,10826,10832,10846,10849,10859,10861,10865,10867,10875,10883,10885,10906,10907,10909,10964,10983,10992,11000,11010,11029,11045,11063,11065,11078,11090,11096,11104,11105,11107	4948,5276,5296,5307,5522,5710,5773,5794,5812,6746,6819,6836,6964,6980,6982,7322,7330,7394,7408,7414,7436,7438,7466,7468,7538,7574,7576,7594,7598,7643,7645,7646,7898,7915,7916,7958,7960,7986,8012,8438,8486,8548,8555,8556,8572,8573,8597,8608,8635,8692,8780,8782,8786,8803,8818,8851,8867,8896,8898,8962,8966,9050,9113,9424,9428,9445,9446,9448,9452,9470,9506,9508,9533,9535,9542,9562,9572,9573,9574,9578,9598,9607,9608,9616,9626,9643,9644,9646,9650,9655,9687,9688,9706,9713,9733,9740,9788,9808,9813,9814,9885,9886,9893,9902,9908,9915,9923,9938,9947,9948,9949,9977,9978,9986,10012,10040,10058,10068,10069,10076,10091,10093,10102,10118,10316,10317,10342,10357,10402,10436,10451,10453,10468,10469,10474,10475,10516,10552,10568,10571,10572,10577,10588,10589,10597,10598,10604,10606,10613,10615,10618,10621,10633,10634,10636,10645,10669,10678,10715,10733,10757,10759,10771,10784,10805,10813,10825,10831,10833,10834,10838,10843,10844,10847,10852,10856,10858,10860,10868,10958,10970,10972,10986,10987,10991,10996,11002,11012,11036,11037,11038,11047,11054,11055,11066,11068,11072,11077,11081,11082,11083,11095,11108

Previously missing decreasing crazy sequential representations (for $\emptyset$ up to 11111):

	Only pseudo crazy sequential representation	No crazy sequential representation
Without Division	9686,10802	9668,11038
Without Potentiation	5819,7166,7195,7222,7682,8276,8285,8293,8482,8528,9302,9497,9532,9626,9733,9949,10022,10310,10412,10468,10545,10667,10768,10802,10805,11029,11038,11056	8258,9668,9970,10316,10498
Without Concatenation	2135,4723,4867,5278,5284,5294,5451,5791,6026,6098,6286,6294,6296,6314,6332,6358,6366,6378,6415,6423,6467,6469,6599,6649,6780,6854,6938,6943,6944,6956,6981,7036,7052,7077,7082,7084,7093,7147,7413,7438,7444,7564,7598,7933,8251,8310,8365,8426,8457,8467,8490,8503,8552,8553,8563,8573,8596,8607,8620,8651,8718,8849,8921,8932,8943,8957,8961,8962,9022,9032,9121,9122,9131,9133,9155,9176,9200,9202,9302,9311,9415,9421,9424,9470,9515,9570,9573,9574,9579,9619,9646,9650,9664,9667,9688,9692,9733,9737,9748,9824,9878,9884,9893,9915,9922,9923,9927,9931,9947,9950,9958,9968,9974,9980,10021,10022,10054,10061,10068,10076,10084,10142,10171,10177,10227,10228,10245,10257,10267,10276,10309,10310,10419,10464,10482,10486,10488,10490,10492,10588,10684,10697,10699,10704,10735,10736,10738,10748,10749,10766,10768,10798,10805,10823,10844,10848,10946,10989,10996,11003,11010,11029,11030,11037,11039,11054,11056,11057,11058,11062,11077,11092,11095	6404,6523,7034,7078,8363,8492,8572,8944,8989,9508,9542,9556,9578,9634,9643,9644,9678,9885,10052,10069,10460,10474,10480,10516,10526,10544,10564,10597,10671,10715,10732,10733,10741,10742,10751,10753,10757,10758,10775,10784,10814,10831,10832,10858,11006,11044,11066,11068

Previously missing increasing crazy sequential representations (for $\emptyset$ down to -11111):

	Only pseudo crazy sequential representation	No crazy sequential representation
Without Division	-7330, -7508, -7526, -7539, -7942, -7996, -8402, -9092, -9340, -9436, -9733, -9806, -9812, -9907, -9925, -9986, -10078, -10085, -10316, -10330, -10346, -10364, -10492, -10636, -10748, -10813, -10820, -11002, -11003, -11012, -11075, -11077, -11080, -11083, -11093, -11099	-10958, -11027
Without Potentiation	-6548, -7330, -7357, -7508, -7576, -7646, -7673, -7942, -7987, -7996, -8014, -8170, -8293, -8324, -8563, -8564, -8795, -8797, -8834, -8851, -8869, -8885, -8887, -9092, -9232, -9302, -9340, -9532, -9733, -9771, -9806, -10020, -10078, -10082, -10084, -10085, -10102, -10129, -10156, -10213, -10222, -10238, -10253, -10264, -10292, -10298, -10316, -10330, -10334, -10346, -10364, -10366, -10388, -10456, -10460, -10492, -10543, -10577, -10636, -10645, -10739, -10748, -10820, -10822, -10828, -10843, -10918, -10931, -10987, -11003, -11012, -11020, -11093, -11102	-8312, -9238, -9986, -10838, -10840, -10886, -10958, -11002, -11027
Without Concatenation	-3460, -3820, -4179, -4468, -4496, -4548, -4558, -4768, -4817, -4827, -4856, -4868, -4886, -4972, -5278, -5295, -5315, -5318, -5332, -5333, -5431, -5443, -5566, -5582, -5666, -5674, -5692, -5699, -5708, -5709, -5739, -5756, -5774, -5792, -5884, -5970, -6266, -6303, -6304, -6378, -6380, -6382, -6388, -6456, -6602, -6700, -6748, -6773, -6788, -6789, -6814, -6815, -6820, -6861, -6926, -6928, -6932, -6933, -6981, -6986, -6995, -6996, -7016, -7328, -7358, -7360, -7365, -7387, -7404, -7405, -7422, -7437, -7445, -7454, -7456, -7472, -7492, -7508, -7518, -7519, -7537, -7539, -7556, -7563, -7571, -7573, -7580, -7597, -7620, -7621, -7654, -7655, -7664, -7675, -7715, -7834, -7868, -7906, -7918, -7942, -7961, -7963, -7964, -7971, -7972, -7996, -8036, -8044, -8067, -8068, -8269, -8291, -8323, -8342, -8346, -8348, -8357, -8362, -8373, -8456, -8488, -8490, -8507, -8508, -8557, -8564, -8565, -8574, -8588, -8590, -8594, -8596, -8606, -8607, -8609, -8617, -8660, -8662, -8698, -8699, -8717, -8723, -8725, -8752, -8770, -8777, -8778, -8779, -8787, -8788, -8798, -8822, -8824, -8833, -8834, -8836, -8842, -8843, -8866, -8888, -8890, -8894, -8897, -8943, -8944, -8957, -8980, -8986, -8987, -8989, -9038, -9093, -9122, -9238, -9247, -9422, -9427, -9436, -9442, -9447, -9491, -9507, -9526, -9553, -9560, -9566, -9580, -9581, -9582, -9591, -9592, -9597, -9625, -9632, -9634, -9654, -9677, -9678, -9680, -9682, -9683, -9686, -9700, -9723, -9731, -9762, -9763, -9785, -9786, -9807, -9812, -9821, -9822, -9824, -9832, -9853, -9863, -9866, -9867, -9868, -9872, -9884, -9890, -9896, -9903, -9907, -9914, -9917, -9919, -9921, -9922, -9924, -9925, -9932, -9934, -9939, -9941, -9958, -9974, -9980, -9988, -10003, -10006, -10014, -10015, -10022, -10045, -10048, -10054, -10055, -10057, -10059, -10070, -10074, -10078, -10094, -10096, -10100, -10114, -10117, -10119, -10121, -10130, -10138, -10163, -10226, -10227, -10228, -10244, -10253, -10254, -10264, -10266, -10274, -10275, -10282, -10283, -10307, -10326, -10338, -10344, -10346, -10356, -10363, -10364, -10372, -10379, -10382, -10388, -10444, -10445, -10462, -10470, -10471, -10480, -10482, -10484, -10490, -10491, -10494, -10495, -10498, -10510, -10518, -10524, -10525, -10526, -10534, -10535, -10542, -10544, -10545, -10546, -10550, -10551, -10553, -10554, -10555, -10559, -10564, -10569, -10573, -10576, -10578, -10579, -10590, -10592, -10596, -10599, -10600, -10607, -10609, -10614, -10619, -10623, -10627, -10630, -10635, -10643, -10667, -10668, -10675, -10677, -10696, -10697, -10698, -10699, -10706, -10724, -10726, -10748, -10754, -10768, -10778, -10793, -10797, -10802, -10807, -10811, -10820, -10821, -10823, -10828, -10830, -10832, -10839, -10846, -10849, -10861, -10865, -10866, -10867, -10869, -10877, -10884, -10886, -10892, -10907, -10909, -10924, -10939, -10964, -10967, -10968, -10969, -10973, -10978, -10995, -11000, -11003, -11011, -11022, -11045, -11046, -11048, -11056, -11062, -11064, -11073, -11075, -11080, -11091, -11092, -11093, -11098, -11106	-4948, -5276, -5296, -5307, -5522, -5710, -5773, -5794, -5812, -6746, -6819, -6836, -6964, -6980, -6982, -7322, -7330, -7394, -7408, -7414, -7436, -7438, -7466, -7468, -7538, -7574, -7576, -7594, -7598, -7643, -7645, -7646, -7898, -7915, -7916, -7958, -7960, -7986, -8012, -8438, -8486, -8548, -8555, -8556, -8572, -8573, -8597, -8608, -8635, -8692, -8780, -8782, -8786, -8803, -8818, -8851, -8867, -8896, -8898, -8962, -8966, -9050, -9113, -9424, -9428, -9445, -9446, -9448, -9452, -9470, -9506, -9508, -9533, -9535, -9542, -9562, -9572, -9573, -9574, -9578, -9598, -9607, -9608, -9616, -9626, -9643, -9644, -9646, -9650, -9655, -9687, -9688, -9706, -9713, -9733, -9740, -9788, -9808, -9813, -9814, -9885, -9886, -9893, -9902, -9908, -9915, -9923, -9938, -9947, -9948, -9949, -9977, -9978, -9986, -10012, -10040, -10058, -10068, -10069, -10076, -10091, -10093, -10102, -10118, -10316, -10317, -10342, -10357, -10402, -10436, -10451, -10453, -10468, -10469, -10474, -10475, -10516, -10552, -10568, -10571, -10572, -10577, -10588, -10589, -10597, -10598, -10604, -10606, -10613, -10615, -10618, -10621, -10633, -10634, -10636, -10645, -10669, -10678, -10715, -10733, -10757, -10759, -10771, -10784, -10805, -10813, -10825, -10831, -10833, -10834, -10838, -10843, -10844, -10847, -10852, -10856, -10858, -10860, -10868, -10958, -10970, -10972, -10986, -10987, -10991, -10996, -11002, -11012, -11036, -11037, -11038, -11047, -11054, -11055, -11066, -11068, -11072, -11077, -11081, -11082, -11083, -11095, -11108

Previously missing decreasing crazy sequential representations (for 0 down to -11111):

	Only pseudo crazy sequential representation	No crazy sequential representation
Without Division	-9508, -9524, -9644, -9767, -9949, -10068, -10526, -10706, -10732, -10802, -10832, -10988	-9668, -11038
Without Potentiation	-7082, -7108, -7171, -7220, -7222, -8122, -8123, -8467, -8539, -8894, -9412, -9508, -9524, -9596, -9616, -9634, -9644, -9650, -9670, -9733, -9767, -10068, -10076, -10085, -10156, -10280, -10309, -10317, -10334, -10411, -10484, -10492, -10526, -10546, -10550, -10553, -10558, -10604, -10636, -10645, -10670, -10732, -10768, -10832, -10882, -10972, -11003, -11038, -11056	-8258, -9668, -9970, -10316, -10498
Without Concatenation	-5276, -5278, -5377, -5387, -5963, -6277, -6285, -6286, -6314, -6351, -6366, -6378, -6388, -6402, -6412, -6415, -6419, -6422, -6437, -6467, -6593, -6595, -6610, -6676, -6872, -6926, -6938, -6944, -6980, -7044, -7045, -7052, -7076, -7077, -7082, -7093, -7413, -7466, -7541, -8309, -8310, -8364, -8428, -8444, -8446, -8482, -8490, -8518, -8542, -8552, -8553, -8562, -8563, -8564, -8573, -8696, -8921, -8933, -8957, -8962, -8974, -8979, -8980, -8988, -9020, -9022, -9031, -9032, -9037, -9067, -9104, -9105, -9114, -9115, -9122, -9123, -9131, -9133, -9148, -9155, -9170, -9172, -9176, -9274, -9355, -9357, -9364, -9406, -9415, -9416, -9428, -9436, -9445, -9493, -9497, -9515, -9518, -9524, -9527, -9543, -9562, -9572, -9573, -9574, -9616, -9628, -9629, -9637, -9646, -9651, -9663, -9669, -9692, -9704, -9733, -9746, -9813, -9820, -9821, -9824, -9853, -9876, -9886, -9915, -9922, -9931, -9971, -10054, -10068, -10084, -10142, -10168, -10172, -10174, -10177, -10222, -10244, -10245, -10253, -10267, -10309, -10310, -10312, -10317, -10330, -10424, -10459, -10461, -10479, -10491, -10492, -10493, -10514, -10515, -10520, -10542, -10545, -10555, -10561, -10565, -10588, -10590, -10604, -10605, -10689, -10714, -10731, -10734, -10739, -10754, -10756, -10762, -10776, -10798, -10810, -10811, -10815, -10833, -10857, -10859, -10860, -10861, -10868, -10910, -11003, -11021, -11028, -11029, -11030, -11055, -11056, -11057, -11058, -11092, -11095, -11104, -11110	-6404, -6523, -7034, -7078, -8363, -8492, -8572, -8944, -8989, -9508, -9542, -9556, -9578, -9634, -9643, -9644, -9678, -9885, -10052, -10069, -10460, -10474, -10480, -10516, -10526, -10544, -10564, -10597, -10671, -10715, -10732, -10733, -10741, -10742, -10751, -10753, -10757, -10758, -10775, -10784, -10814, -10831, -10832, -10858, -11006, -11044, -11066, -11068

Results

Twenty previously unknown crazy sequential representations were identified:

Integer	Without Concatenation	Integer	Without Concatenation
8555	$-1+(2+3^4*5)*(6+7+8)+9$	-8555	$1-(2+3^4*5)*(6+7+8)-9$
8556	$1*(2+3^4*5)*(6+7+8)+9$	-8556	$-1*(2+3^4*5)*(6+7+8)-9$
8608	$(-1*2+(3/4)^{-5})*6^7/(8*9)$	-8608	$(-1*2+(3/4)^{-5})*-6^7/(8*9)$
8851	$1*(2*3^4+5)*(6+7*8-9)$	-8851	$-1*(2*3^4+5)*(6+7*8-9)$
9947	$(1-2^3)^4*(5-6*7^8(8-9))$	-9947	$(1-2^3)^4*(-5+6*7^8(8-9))$
10825	$1+(((-2+3)*4)^5/6*7+8)*9$	-10825	$-1-(((-2+3)*4)^5/6*7+8)*9$
10833	$(1+((2^3-4)^5/6*7)+8)*9$	-10833	$(1+((2^3-4)^5/6*7)+8)*-9$
11072	$1*2+(3^4-5+6)*(7+8)*9$	-11072	$1*-2-(3^4-5+6)*(7+8)*9$
11095	$1^2+(3^4+5)*(-6+(7+8)*9)$	-11095	$1*2-3^4*(5*(6+7)+8*9)$
Integer	Without Division/Potentiation	Integer	Without Division/Potentiation
10102	$1+(-2+3*-4*56)*(-7-8)-9$	-10102	$-1+(-2+3*-4*56)*(7+8)+9$

After simplification;

- 1370 out of 1384 pseudo crazy sequential representations became genuine.
- 13721 out of 133344 crazy sequential representations became shorter.

Currently missing genuine crazy sequential representations:

	Increasing	Decreasing
Without Division	-10958, -11027 10958, 11027	-9668, -11038 9668, 11038
Without Potentiation	-8312, -9238, -9986, -10838, -10840, -10886, -10958, -11002, -11027 8312, 9238, 9986, 10838, 10840, 10886, 10958, 11002, 11027	-8258, -9668, -9970, -10316, -10498 8258, 9668, 9970, 10316, 10498
Without Concatenation	-4948, -5276, -5296, -5307, -5522, -5710, -5773, -5794, -5812, -6746, -6819, -6836, -6964, -6980, -6982, -7322, -7330, -7394, -7408, -7414, -7436, -7438, -7466, -7468, -7538, -7574, -7576, -7594, -7598, -7643, -7645, -7646, -7898, -7915, -7916, -7958, -7960, -7986, -8012, -8438, -8486, -8548, -8572, -8573, -8597, -8635, -8692, -8780, -8782, -8786, -8803, -8818, -8867, -8896, -8898, -8962, -8966, -9050, -9113, -9424, -9428, -9445, -9446, -9448, -9452, -9470, -9506, -9508, -9533, -9535, -9542, -9562, -9572, -9573, -9574, -9578, -9598, -9607, -9608, -9616, -9626, -9643, -9644, -9646, -9650, -9655, -9687, -9688, -9706, -9713, -9733, -9740, -9788, -9808, -9813, -9814, -9885, -9886, -9893, -9902, -9908, -9915, -9923, -9938, -9948, -9949, -9977, -9978, -9986, -10012, -10040, -10058, -10068, -10069, -10076, -10091, -10093, -10102, -10118, -10316, -10317, -10342, -10357, -10402, -10436, -10451, -10453, -10468, -10469, -10474, -10475, -10516, -10552, -10568, -10571, -10572, -10577, -10588, -10589, -10597, -10598, -10604, -10606, -10613, -10615, -10618, -10621, -10633, -10634, -10636, -10645, -10669, -10678, -10715, -10733, -10757, -10759, -10771, -10784, -10805, -10813, -10831, -10834, -10838, -10843, -10844, -10847, -10852, -10856, -10858, -10860, -10868, -10958, -10970, -10972, -10986, -10987, -10991, -10996, -11002, -11012, -11036, -11037, -11038, -11047, -11054, -11055, -11066, -11068, -11077, -11081, -11082, -11083, -11108	-6404, -6523, -7034, -7078, -8363, -8492, -8572, -8944, -8989, -9508, -9542, -9556, -9578, -9634, -9643, -9644, -9678, -9885, -10052, -10069, -10460, -10474, -10480, -10516, -10526, -10544, -10564, -10597, -10671, -10715, -10732, -10733, -10741, -10742, -10751, -10753, -10757, -10758, -10775, -10784, -10814, -10831, -10832, -10858, -11006, -11044, -11066, -11068
	-5756, -6602, -6700, -6788, -6820, -6926, -6928, -6981, -9677, -9686	-9022, -10815
	4948, 5276, 5296, 5307, 5522, 5710, 5773, 5794, 5812, 6746, 6819, 6836, 6964, 6980, 6982, 7322, 7330, 7394, 7408, 7414, 7436, 7438, 7466, 7468, 7538, 7574, 7576, 7594, 7598, 7643, 7645, 7646, 7898, 7915, 7916, 7958, 7960, 7986, 8012, 8438, 8486, 8548, 8572, 8573, 8597, 8635, 8692, 8780, 8782, 8786, 8803, 8818, 8867, 8896, 8898, 8962, 8966, 9050, 9113, 9424, 9428, 9445, 9446, 9448, 9452, 9470, 9506, 9508, 9533, 9535, 9542, 9562, 9572, 9573, 9574, 9578, 9598, 9607, 9608, 9616, 9626, 9643, 9644, 9646, 9650, 9655, 9687, 9688, 9706, 9713, 9733, 9740, 9788, 9808, 9813, 9814, 9885, 9886, 9893, 9902, 9908, 9915, 9923, 9938, 9948, 9949, 9977, 9978, 9986, 10012, 10040, 10058, 10068, 10069, 10076, 10091, 10093, 10102, 10118, 10316, 10317, 10342, 10357, 10402, 10436, 10451, 10453, 10468, 10469, 10474, 10475, 10516, 10552, 10568, 10571, 10572, 10577, 10588, 10589, 10597, 10598, 10604, 10606, 10613, 10615, 10618, 10621, 10633, 10634, 10636, 10645, 10669, 10678, 10715, 10733, 10757, 10759, 10771, 10784, 10805, 10813, 10831, 10834, 10838, 10843, 10844, 10847, 10852, 10856, 10858, 10860, 10868, 10958, 10970, 10972, 10986, 10987, 10991, 10996, 11002, 11012, 11036, 11037, 11038, 11047, 11054, 11055, 11066, 11068, 11077, 11081, 11082, 11083, 11108	6404, 6523, 7034, 7078, 8363, 8492, 8572, 8944, 8989, 9508, 9542, 9556, 9578, 9634, 9643, 9644, 9678, 9885, 10052, 10069, 10460, 10474, 10480, 10516, 10526, 10544, 10564, 10597, 10671, 10715, 10732, 10733, 10741, 10742, 10751, 10753, 10757, 10758, 10775, 10784, 10814, 10831, 10832, 10858, 11006, 11044, 11066, 11068
	9568	

Supplements

Shortest genuine crazy sequential representations were tabulated in the supplements;

- Supplement 1 Increasing for 0 up to 11111
- Supplement 2 Decreasing for 0 up to 11111
- Supplement 3 Increasing for 1 down to -11111
- Supplement 4 Decreasing for 1 down to -11111

Note; pseudo crazy sequential representations were tabulated for the integers in green.

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Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019

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Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
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A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
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A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
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A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 09 Jan 2019
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A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Friday 04 Jan 2019
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Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####)
A.E. Bras, V.H.J. van der Velden. Wednesday 23 Jan 2019